

MUTRAKRICHHRA AND LOWER URINARY TRACT INFECTIONS (LUTIS): INTEGRATING CLASSICAL AYURVEDA WITH CONTEMPORARY UROLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Mutrakrichhra is a prevalent condition in Ayurvedic and community practice, encompassing a range of urinary disorders that correspond to Lower urinary tract infections (LUTIs) in modern medicine. The hallmark symptom, *pratyatma lakshana*, is “*Dukhena mutra pravritti*”—painful or difficult micturition. *Mutrakrichhra* may occur as an independent disease or as a symptom in conditions such as *Ashmari*, *Mutraghata*, *Mutraja Vriddhi*, *Arsha*, and *Gulma*. Its pathogenesis involves aggravated *pitta dosha*, in combination with *Vata* (particularly *Apana Vayu*), affecting the *basti* (urinary bladder) and *Mutravaha Srotas*, producing clinical features including *Daha* (burning sensation), *ruja* (pain), *shotha* (edema), *bastigurutva* (heaviness of bladder), *Muhurmutrata* (frequent urination), *peetamutrata* (yellow urine), and *sarakta mutrata* (hematuria). The symptomatology closely parallels LUTIs such as urethritis and cystitis. *Nidana* factors, including dietary and lifestyle errors, alter urine composition, creating an environment

conducive to microbial growth. Classical Ayurvedic management emphasizes *Chikitsa* and *Oushadha Yogas* with diuretic and antimicrobial properties to restore *doshic* balance and relieve symptoms. A critical analysis of *Mutrakrichhra* underscores its clinical correlation with modern LUTIs, highlighting the relevance of Ayurvedic principles in understanding, preventing, and managing urinary tract disorders.

KEYWORDS: *Mutrakrichhra*, Lower urinary tract infections, *Mutravaha Srotas*, *Ayurvedic* management.

INTRODUCTION

“*Mutram kledavahanam jneyam, Shonitasya prasadanaam*”—*Mutra* (urine) is considered essential for the elimination of *kleda* and for maintaining the purity of *Rakta dhatu*. Among the *Trimala*^[1], *Mutra* plays a vital role in homeostasis. *Mutravega* (urge of urination) is classified as an *Adharaniya Vega*^[2] (a natural urge not to be suppressed), and *Basti* (urinary bladder), being the *Srotomula* of *Mutra*, is also counted among the *Trimarma*^[3], highlighting its crucial physiological significance.

Mutrakrichhra is one of the urinary disorders elaborately described by *Acharyas*, denoting *Krichhrata in Mutravahana*—difficulty in passing urine. The *Ayurvedic* texts detail its *Nidana* (etiology), *Bheda* (types), *Lakshana* (clinical features), and *Chikitsa* (management).

From a modern perspective, the etiopathogenesis and clinical features of *Mutrakrichhra* closely resemble those of Urinary Tract Infection (UTI), particularly Lower Urinary Tract Infections (LUTIs). The urinary system is divided into the upper tract (kidneys and ureters) and the lower tract (bladder, urethra, and prostate).^[4] LUTIs, encompassing cystitis and urethritis, is among the most prevalent bacterial infections, with an estimated 150 million cases annually worldwide. The condition is especially common in women, as 50–80% of females experience at least one episode during their lifetime.^[5]

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

- To understand the *Ayurvedic* concept of *Mutrakrichhra* in detail.
- To review the modern medical understanding of Lower urinary tract infections (LUTIs).
- To compare the signs, symptoms, and pathogenesis of *Mutrakrichhra* with those of Lower urinary tract infections (LUTIs).
- To explore the relevance of *Ayurvedic* diagnosis and treatment of *Mutrakrichhra* in the context of modern LUTIs management.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

All the relevant literature and information on *Mutrakrichhra* were collected from classical *Ayurvedic* texts, while data on Lower urinary tract infections (LUTIs) were obtained from standard modern medical sources.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Nidana of Mutrakrichhra^[6]

- *Ahara* (Dietary factors): - *Atisevana* of *ruksha, ushna, katu, tikshna* ahara (excessive dry, hot, spicy, irritant food) - *Madhyasevana* (alcohol intake) - *Anupamatsya sevana* (excess fish, heavy food) - *Adhyashana* (overeating) - *Ajirna, Viruddhahara* (indigestion, incompatible diet).
- *Vihara* (Lifestyle factors): - *Ativyayama* (excessive exertion) - *Nityadruta prushthayata* (excessive riding/strain) - *Mutravegadharana* (suppression of urination).
- *Oushadha* (Drug-related): - *Teekshna aushadha sevana* (excess use of strong/irritant medicines).
- *Samanya Hetu*: - Vitiating of *Vata* (causing obstruction & pain) - Vitiating of *Pitta* (causing burning & inflammation) - Vitiating of *Kapha* (causing turbidity & sliminess in urine).

Etiology of LUTIs^[7]

- Causative organisms: - *Escherichia coli* (80–85% cases) - *Klebsiella pneumoniae* - *Proteus mirabilis* - *Staphylococcus saprophyticus*.
- Predisposing factors: - Poor genital hygiene - Sexual activity (short urethra in females) - Vaginal ecology disturbances - Foreign body/catheterization.
- Medical conditions: - Diabetes mellitus - Immunosuppression - Urinary obstruction (stone, stricture) - Neurogenic bladder.
- Other risk factors: - Genetic susceptibility (family history, recurrent UTI in young women) - Ascending infection route (urethra → bladder → kidney if untreated).

Samprapti of Mutrakrichhra^[8]

Pathogenesis of LUTIs^[9]

Virulence factors of uropathogens (esp. *E. coli*, *Proteus*)

Fimbriae (adhesion)

Haemolysin, Aerobactin (serum resistance)

O antigen & K capsular antigen

Siderophores

Urease

|

Enhanced colonisation → Toxin release → Replication

|

Antibiotic resistance & Iron trapping by *E. coli*

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Development of LUTIs

Samprapti Ghatak of Mutrakrichhra.

1	<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Tridosha with dominant Vata (Su.), Pitta (Ka.)</i>
2	<i>Dushya</i>	<i>Mutra, Rasa, Rakta (predominantly)</i>
3	<i>Agni</i>	<i>Jatharagni Mandya, Dhatwagni Mandya</i>
4	<i>Aama</i>	<i>Jatharagni-mandya-janya Ama</i>
5	<i>Srotas</i>	<i>Mutravaha Srotas, Rasayanee</i>
6	<i>Srotodushti Prakara</i>	<i>Sanga</i>
7	<i>Adhithana</i>	<i>Mutrashaya</i>
8	<i>Sanchara Sthana</i>	<i>Rasayanee, Sarva Shareera</i>
9	<i>Vyaktasthana</i>	<i>Mutravaha Srotas</i>
10	<i>Rogamarga</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
11	<i>Roga Prakruti</i>	<i>Nija, Agantuja</i>
12	<i>Roga Prabhava</i>	<i>Krichhrata in Mutra Pravritti</i>

Bheda (According to various classics).

Sl.No.	Types of <i>Mutrakrichhra</i>	C.S	S.S	A.H	A.S	M.N	Y.R	B.P	K.S	B.S	G.N	C.D
1	<i>Vataja</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
2	<i>Pittaja</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
3	<i>Kaphaja</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
4	<i>Sannipataja</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
5	<i>Dwandwaja</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6	<i>Raktaja</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7	<i>Pureeshaja</i>	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

8	<i>Shukraja</i>	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
9	<i>Sharkaraja</i>	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
10	<i>Ashmarija</i>	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
11	<i>Shalya-abhighataja</i>	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Purvarupa

In Ayurvedic literature, the premonitory symptoms of *Mutrakrichhra* have not been described. A similar observation is also noted in contemporary science.

Samanya Lakshana of Mutrakrichhra^[10]

These are the **common features seen in all types**

- ***Kruchrata in Mutravahana*** – difficulty in micturition (*cardinal symptom*).
- ***Ushnadhara (Sadahamutrata)*** – burning sensation while urinating.
- ***Mutrasrotodushti*** – dysfunction of urinary passages.
- ***Raktapravritti*** – haematuria (blood in urine).

(Mentioned in *Madhukosha commentary of Madhava Nidana* and by *Acharya Harita*).

Vishista Lakshana of Mutrakrichhra

- ***Vataja Mutrakrichhra^[11]***: *Vankshanashula* – pain in inguinal region, *Bastishula* – suprapubic pain, *Medhrashula* – pain in penis/urethra, *Muhurmuhur mutrapravartana* – increased frequency of urination, *Alpamutrata* – scanty urine, *Phenamutrata* – frothy urine, *Arunamutrata* – reddish urine, *Avarchastvam* – difficulty in defecation.
- ***Pittaja Mutrakrichhra^[11]***: *Sadahamutrata* – intense burning urination (*pradhana lakshana*), *Daha in mushka & mehana pradesha* – burning in scrotal/penile region, *Saruja mutrata* – painful urination, *Muhurmutrata* – frequency of urination, *Peeta/Haridra mutrata* – yellow urine, *Krushna mutrata* – dark urine, *Sarakta mutrata* – hematuria, *Ushna bashpa samhita* – feverish sensation with sweating.
- ***Kaphaja Mutrakrichhra^[11]***: *Shotha & Gurutwa of basti, linga, mushka* – swelling & heaviness of bladder, penis, scrotum, *Picchila mutrata* – slimy urine, *Shukla mutrata* – whitish urine, *Anushna mutra* – non-burning urine, *Samrushtaroma* – horripilation, *Vibandha* – constipation, *Alpamutrata* – scanty urination.
- ***Sannipataja Mutrakrichhra^[11]***: Symptoms of all three doshas combined, *Daha* – burning micturition, *Ruja* – pain during micturition, *Nanavarna mutra* – multi-colored urine,

Muhurmutrata – frequent urination, *Murchha*, *Bhrama* – fainting, giddiness, *Vilepa* – feeling of uneasiness.

- ***Abhighataja Mutrakrichhra*^[12]**: *Basti-kukshi peeda* – lower abdominal pain, *Kruchramutrata* – painful/difficult urination. (Similar to *Vataja* type due to *Vata prakopa* after trauma/foreign body).
- ***Shakrutaja Mutrakrichhra*^[12]**: *Adhamana* – abdominal distension, *Shula* – pain, *Mutrasanga* – retention of urine.
- ***Ashmarija Mutrakrichhra***: *Vedana in basti, sevani, mehana* – pain in bladder, perineum, penis, *Visheernadhara mutra* – interrupted urinary stream, *Dourbalya* – weakness^[13], Symptoms overlap with *Ashmari*^[14] (urolithiasis).
- ***Shukraja Mutrakrichhrap*^[15]**: *Mutra pravritti mixed with shukra (semen)*, *Vedana in bladder & penis*, *Vrushana ativrutta* – enlarged, painful testicles, *Vibandha of mutra & shukra* – obstructed urination/ejaculation, *Tudyate vedana* – pricking type of pain.
- ***Raktaja Mutrakrichhra*^[16]**: *Teevra artti* – excruciating pain, *Raktamutrata* – hematuria, *Aadhamana & Gaurava in basti*, *Laghutwa* after passage of clot/stone.
- ***Vatakundali Mutrakrichhra*^[17]**: *Mutralpatwa* – scanty urine, *Vedana* – pain, *Adhamana* – distension, *Gurutwa* – heaviness, *Kandu* – itching.

Clinical Features of LUTIs^[18]

- Abrupt onset of frequency of urination, urgency (sudden compelling desire to void), dysuria (burning pain in urethra during micturition), nocturia (increased urination at night), urge incontinence (involuntary leakage of urine with urgency), suprapubic pain (bladder region discomfort), sensation of incomplete bladder emptying (due to spasm of inflamed bladder wall), urine abnormalities such as offensive smell, cloudy appearance, and presence of blood (hematuria).

Chikitsa of *Mutrakrichhra*

1. ***Vataja Mutrakrichhra Chikitsa***: *Vata nashaka taila abhyanga, sneha and niruha basti, sneha dravya upanaha, utara basti, parisheka on katipradesha with vatanashaka taila, siradi varga and vatanashaka dravya, shadanga paniya mixed with mamsarasa.*

2. **Pittaja Mutrakrichhra Chikitsa:** *Parisheka, avagaha, pradeha* with *sheetala dravya*, following *Grishma rutucharya, basti, kshirapan* and *virechana*, use of *draksharasa, vidarikand, swaasa, ikshu rasa, ghrita*, and *pittanashaka dravyas*.
3. **Kaphaja Mutrakrichhra Chikitsa:** *Kshara, ushna, tikshna* and *katurasa annapana, swedana, yava-anna, niruha basti* with *takra*, use of *tikta varga aushadhi taila pana* and *abhyanga*.
4. **Tridoshaja Mutrakrichhra Chikitsa:** Treatment depends on *sthana* and predominance of *dosha*. If *Kapha pradhana*, then *vamana*. If *Pitta adhikya*, then *virechana*. If *Vata* involvement, then *basti*.
5. **Ashmari Sharkara Mutrakrichhra Chikitsa;** Same principles as *Kapha* and *Vata* chikitsa.
6. **Sukraja Mutrakrichhra Chikitsa:** Treatment according to the predominating vitiated *dosha*.
7. **Raktaja Mutrakrichhra Chikitsa:** Stem of *Neel Kamal, Taal, Kaasa, Ikshuval, Ikshumoola*, and *Kasheru* — taken in equal quantity, prepare *kwatha* with *sitaa* or *madhu* and administer orally, to lick: *ikshu*, to eat: *vidarikanda churna* and *trapusha*. *Pittaja mutraroga chikitsa* can also be adopted.

Formulations Used in *Mutrakrichhra*^[19]

- **Kwatha/Kashaya** - *Varunshigruadi kwatha, Gokshuradi kwatha, Varunadi kwatha, Bruhathyadi kashayam, Shatavaryadi kwatha, Haritakyadi kwatha, Trinapanchmula kwatha, Shwadanshtradi kwatha, Pashanbhedadi yoga, Gudadugdha yoga, Dhatriyadi yoga, Amritadi kwatha, Sthiradi aushadha*.
- **Asava** - *Chandanasava*.
- **Gutika & Rasoushadhi** - *Chandraprabha vati, Gokshuradi guggulu, Trivikrama rasa, Chandrakala rasa*.
- **Ghrita** - *Trikankantakadi ghrita*.
- **Taila** - *Shwadanshtra taila, Traivritta taila, Mishraka sneha*.
- **Choorna & Bhasma** - *Trinapanchamula choorna, choorna of Ervaru beeja, Yashtimadhu, Devdaru with Tandul dhavan, Vyoshadi choorna, Praval bhasma*.

Pathya–Apathya in Mutrakrichhra^[20]

Pathya: *Purana Lohita Shali* (old red rice), alkaline foods, *Yava anna* (barley diet), *Ushna* and *Teekshna* buttermilk, milk, curd, *Dhanwa Mamsa* (meat of forest animals), *Mudga Rasa* (green gram soup), *Sita* (sugar, in moderation), *Kushmanda Phala* (ash gourd), *Patola*, *Maha Ardraka*, *Gokshura*, *Kumari*, *Arka* nut, *Khajura* (dates), *Narikela* (coconut), fruits of *Tala Vruksha*, *Masthaka Majja*, *Trapusaphala*, *Trudi*, and cold drinks.

Apathya: *Madhya Pana* (alcohol), *Ati-vyayama* (excessive physical exertion), *Ati-vyavaya* (excessive sexual intercourse), *Vega-rodhana* (suppression of natural urges), *Viruddha Ahara* and *Vishamashana* (incompatible and irregular diet), pan chewing (betel leaf), fish, excess salt, ginger fried in gingelly oil, use of *Pinyaka*, *Hingu*, *Tila*, *Sarshapa* (oil cakes, asafoetida, sesame, mustard), use of *Masha* (black gram), *Kareera Phala*, *Ati Ushna* and *Teekshna Ahara* (excessively hot and penetrating foods), *Ruksha* and *Amla Ahara* (excessively dry and sour foods and drinks), and an excessively hot, spicy, pungent diet causing a burning sensation.

DISCUSSION

The disease *Mutrakrichhra*, as described in *Ayurvedic* texts, and Lower Urinary Tract Infection (LUTIs) in modern medicine share remarkable similarities in their etiology, pathogenesis, and clinical features.

On the basis of Nidana

In LUTIs, the primary factors contributing to the disease are changes in the pH or concentration of urine, along with the host's immune status and genitourinary health. Similarly, in *Ayurveda*, the *nidanas* of *Mutrakrichhra* include factors that alter urine concentration or reduce body resistance, such as indulgence in *ruksha ahara*, *ativyayama*, *mutravegadharana*, and other lifestyle-related causes. This shows that both systems recognize internal as well as external precipitating factors.

On the basis of Lakshana.

<i>Mutrakrichhra</i> Lakshanas (<i>Ayurveda</i>)	Clinical Features of LUTI (Modern Medicine)
<i>Krichhrata</i> in <i>Mutravahana</i> – difficulty/painful micturition	Dysuria – burning pain during urination
<i>Muhur-muhur Mutrapravritti</i> – frequent urination	Frequency & urgency of urination
<i>Alpamutrata</i> – scanty urination	Sensation of incomplete emptying (due to bladder spasm)

<i>Sadahamutrata (Pitta lakshana)</i> – burning urination	Burning micturition (Dysuria)
<i>Bastishula, Vankshanashula</i> – suprapubic/inguinal pain	Suprapubic pain & discomfort
<i>Raktamutrata</i> – blood in urine	Hematuria (blood in urine)
<i>Picchila / Phenila Mutra</i> – turbid, frothy urine	Cloudy urine (due to pus, WBCs, bacteria)
<i>Gourava / Shotha in Basti (Kapha lakshana)</i> – heaviness, swelling in bladder area	Urge incontinence, nocturia due to bladder wall irritation
<i>Ushnabashpa Samhita (Pitta lakshana)</i> – feverish feeling with sweating	Systemic discomfort (malaise, burning, sometimes low-grade fever)
<i>Dourbalya, Laghutwa after mutra pravritti</i>	Relief after urination , but persistent discomfort

On the basis of *Samprapti*

The *Samprapti* of *Mutrakrichhra* in *Ayurveda* and the pathogenesis of LUTIs in modern medicine differ in approach but show clinical parallels. In *Ayurveda*, causative factors (*Nidana*) like improper diet, behavior, or seasonal changes cause *Tridosha* imbalance, leading to *Ama* formation and obstruction in the *Mutramarga* (*Basti* and urinary channels), with tissue damage due to *Dhatu-kshaya* and *Ojo-kshaya*. *Ama* acts as an internal toxin, and reduced *Vyadhikshamatwa* from *Kleda* disturbance weakens immunity. In contrast, modern medicine identifies bacterial entry (mainly *E. coli*) through poor hygiene or sexual activity, with ascending infection from urethra to bladder. Bacterial adhesion, toxin release, and immune evasion cause inflammation and tissue injury. While *Ayurveda* views the disease as a result of internal imbalance, modern medicine describes a microbial infection pathway.

Clinically, both present with painful, burning urination, frequency, urgency, and in severe cases, systemic symptoms—*Ayurveda* attributes it to *Dosha* imbalance, while modern science links it to bacterial spread and possible complications like pyelonephritis or sepsis.

On the basis of *Chikitsa*

The *Ayurvedic* management of *Mutrakrichhra* includes *Shodhana*, *Sthanika Chikitsa*, and *Shamana Oushadhi*, using therapies like *Basti*, *Uttara Basti*, and herbs such as *Gokshura*, *Punarnava*, and *Pashanabheda* with *Mutrala*, *Shothahara*, and *Krimighna* properties. These aim to balance *Doshas*, reduce inflammation, and clear urinary obstruction. In contrast, modern management of LUTIs involves antibiotics (e.g., Nitrofurantoin, Ciprofloxacin), urinary alkalizers, and hydration, targeting bacterial elimination and symptom relief directly without purification procedures.

CONCLUSION

Mutrakrichhra, a urinary system disorder, exhibits symptoms that closely resemble those of Urinary Tract Infection (UTI) in modern medicine. The distinguishing feature of *Mutrakrichhra* is difficulty in micturition, which differentiates it from *Mutraghata*, characterized by relative or absolute *anuria*. The therapeutic approach primarily focuses on the use of *Vatahara* drugs with *Madhura Rasa*, *Madhura Vipaka*, and *Shita Virya* are emphasized, as these qualities pacify both *Vata* and *Pitta Dosha*, thereby proving effective in conditions like *Vataja Mutrakrichhra* and *Pittaja Mutrakrichhra*. Conversely, formulations containing *Katu* and *Tikta Rasa*, *Tikshna Guna*, and *Ushna Virya* act by clearing the obstructions in the urinary pathway (*Srotoshodhana*), normalizing the flow of *Mutra* and *Rakta*, and pacifying *Kapha Dosha*, making them beneficial in *Kaphaja Mutrakrichhra*.

These pharmacological attributes collectively contribute to the breakdown of the *Samprapti* (pathogenesis) of *Mutrakrichhra*. Alongside drug therapy, proper *Pathya–Apathya* regimen is highlighted as a supportive factor, which not only aids recovery but also prevents recurrence.

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